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HRJust WP 5 - Migration

Memo: Civil Society Engagement Summary I

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Civil Society Engagement Summary I

I. Introduction

On February 21 and March 7, 2025, we conducted two separate focus group interviews with representatives from civil society organizations engaged in immigration policy, human rights protection, and grassroots advocacy. The first session included representatives from the Taiwan Association for Human Rights (TAHR), the Domestic Caretakers Union Taoyuan (DCU), the Taiwan International Workers' Association (TIWA), and Amnesty International Taiwan Section. The second session brought together participants from the TransAsia Sisters Association, Taiwan (TASAT), Covenant Watch, the Taoyuan Migrant Service Center of the People's Service Association, and, again, a representative from the Taiwan Association for Human Rights.

The discussions centered on the following questions:

1. Have they observed the use of HRJ in government discourse? What reasons does the government give for rejecting their rights advocacy?
2. If HRJ have been observed, what are their distinctive features, particularly in the context of migrants?
3. What are their thoughts on resisting HRJ?

This report synthesizes responses from both sessions. We categorized participants' perspectives according to the types of immigrant status they work with: (1) marriage migrants, (2) domestic care workers, (3) fishery workers, (4) factory workers, and (5) refugees. This classification concretely illustrates how policy discourse interacts with the lived conditions of various immigrant communities and reveals underlying patterns of institutional exclusion.

A common observation across these cases is that the HRJ rhetoric encountered by our participants tends to be highly paternalistic and opportunistic. The meaning of "human rights" is often vague or even distorted. Rather than being guided by consistent legal standards, it is often framed in terms of protection or the benefits of the stakeholders themselves. As a result, "human rights" have been reduced to a pretext for deflecting responsibility and reinforcing control, which in turn intensify the very structure of exclusion and social discrimination that human rights are meant to counter.

In the following sections, we first present examples that participants found troubling in the government's responses to their advocacy efforts across different types of migration. It should be noted that these troubling responses are not all instances of HRJ; some are disguised in terms of national interest, economic considerations, or a lack of political consensus. Paternalistic use of HRJ is only one form of disappointing political language that our participants encountered. We then summarize how participants view HRJ as a unique challenge to advancing their agendas, and we conclude with their perspectives on resisting HRJ rhetoric.

II. Troubling Responses

1. Human Trafficking Victims: Isolation as Protection

Taiwan's victim protection scheme requires that victims be relocated and strictly confined in government-run shelters. Their outside contacts are cut off, including communication with supporting organizations and NGOs. Since NGOs are not informed of the victims' whereabouts, it becomes difficult to provide timely material, legal, or psychological assistance. The government justifies detaining victims under conditions even harsher than those faced by pensioners, claiming it is necessary to "protect" their safety. However, the relocation and isolation measures—along with unfriendly administrative procedures—are not necessarily in compliance with the law or consistent with due process, let alone considerate of the hardship they cause for detained victims. Yet these practices are still framed as being in the victims' best interests.

The strong intervention of human trafficking protection measures extends to children of migrant workers born in Taiwan. The Immigration Agency requires migrant worker mothers to file a report before taking their children back to their home country, again citing the rationale of protection—specifically, preventing children from becoming victims of human trafficking.

2. Marriage Immigrants: Paternalistic and Nationalist Exclusion

Marriage immigration in Taiwan is a highly gendered phenomenon, with a relatively high percentage of foreign spouses being women from Southeast Asian countries. Participants observed a shift in the government's rhetoric used to justify rejecting benefits for marriage immigrants. In the past, the government did not shy away from rationales that prioritized nationals' interests or reflected state-centric, sexist considerations. For instance, it justified restrictive visa requirements for marriage immigrants—such as demonstrating financial capability—by claiming they were necessary to prevent "foreign disturbance" to the "local marriage market." Such explicitly sexist and racist considerations are no longer acceptable today. The government has since shifted to framing similar policies as ensuring self-sufficiency "for the good of the immigrant's family" or even "to protect their rights." Despite this rhetorical change, the discriminatory effects experienced by marriage immigrants persist.

Similar shifts can be observed in cases concerning the residency status of immigrant women who are victims of domestic violence. In the past, policies dictated that marriage immigrants would lose their residency if they divorced, even in cases involving domestic violence. Although the rules have since been loosened, a divorced marriage immigrant's residency is still tied to her qualified motherhood and victim status in the eyes of the state. She must be granted custody of minor children and obtain a court protection order to maintain her residency. If a divorced mother does not win custody, she must prove that she visits her children regularly. This requirement to demonstrate being a dutiful mother arguably sets a higher bar than that imposed on other categories of immigrants who apply for residency independently of children and without such stressful circumstances. The government claims these restrictions are "to protect mothers and children," but in reality, they render immigrant women even more vulnerable when facing threats of violence and the subsequent breakdown of marriage or family.

Marriage immigrants have long been expected to serve as caregivers within their families, but when they grow older and become recipients of care and benefits, the government often seeks ways to exclude them from eligibility. For instance, all social aid and social security are tied to legal nationality. Marriage immigrants who have not obtained a Taiwan national ID card (meaning they have not been legally

naturalized) are excluded from financial aid, ostensibly to maintain the financial sustainability of the social security system and thereby “protect nationals’ rights.” They are also excluded from low-income household subsidies. The government argues that including them would disadvantage low-income households as a whole, claiming that because many are the family’s breadwinners, counting their income toward the total household income could raise the sum above the eligibility threshold. However, this reasoning rings hollow for many foreign spouses, as they face a discriminatory labor market and often earn less than the minimum wage—or nothing at all. In many cases, their inclusion would not affect the household’s eligibility for aid. A recent amendment to the Public Assistance Act eased restrictions slightly by allowing aids for those with minor children, but the fundamental exclusion remains unresolved. Foreign spouses still lack adequate economic support and social security.

Based on the same logic that limits social security to nationals, the government denies foreign spouses access to the long-term care system unless they are legally naturalized. Notably, Taiwan does not allow naturalization without renouncing one’s original nationality. This requirement reflects an asymmetrical standard between immigrants and emigrants: while dual citizenship for foreign immigrants is prohibited, dual citizenship for Taiwanese emigrants is permitted. However, such a ban disregards the difficulties faced by many foreign spouses to renounce their origin nationality. If further constitutes discrimination against marriage immigrants and violates their right to social security—particularly for those who have obtained permanent residency. However, this violation is easily dismissed by invoking nationals’ human rights to a sustainable social security system. Currently, immigrants’ long-term care needs are supported only through emergency relief provided by the New Immigrant Development Fund. However, this assistance is limited in scope and incapable of addressing sustained care demands.

Another pressing issue concerns equal access to justice and healthcare with adequate language support. The government and legislators have often dismissed the need for interpreter services, arguing that new immigrants should integrate by learning Mandarin. The Ministry of the Interior reinforced this view by claiming that existing support was sufficient, successfully persuading legislators to retract relevant bills to extend language services. As a result, a national-level interpretation system was never established, leaving immigrants vulnerable in both healthcare and legal proceedings. While the government offers superficial statements of support for providing interpretation services to new immigrants, in practice it has shown no genuine commitment to ensuring such services are available.

In the context of transnational same-sex marriage, the government often cites “national security” as a reason to deny recognition of marriages between Taiwanese citizens and partners from China, Hong Kong, or Macau. In these cases, it argues that the rights of minorities should not compromise the interests of the majority, leading to reluctance in enacting the necessary legal provisions to allow same-sex couples from Taiwan and (mainland) China to marry directly in Taiwan.

3. Foreign Domestic Caregivers and Fishermen: Priority of Nationals’ Rights

The substandard working conditions of foreign domestic caregivers and fishermen have drawn significant attention from NGOs and the National Human Rights Commission. Participants noted that the government often prioritizes the human rights of nationals to resist calls for tighter legal regulations on these workers’ conditions, arguing that such reforms would raise employers’ costs. For example,

when advocacy groups push for higher wages, adequate paid leave, and the right for domestic caregivers to change employers, the government—aligning itself with employer interest groups—rejects these proposals by invoking the “human rights of families with a disabled member.”

The human rights situation of distant-water fishermen is especially dire, as their working conditions inherently require isolation at sea. No timely remedy is available if they face wage shortages, violence, abuse, or urgent medical needs. Suggestions for raising legal standards for fishermen are frequently dismissed on the grounds of “industrial comparative competitiveness.” For instance, proposals to include foreign fishermen in the compulsory labor insurance system have been rejected by officials and industry representatives, who argue that higher social insurance contributions would drive away investment and capital. They claim that fishing boat owners would simply reflag their vessels under less regulated jurisdictions, thereby harming Taiwan’s fishing industry as a whole.

Some improvements—such as making Wi-Fi access compulsory on fishing boats—could easily reduce fishermen’s isolation and vulnerability without incurring high costs or requiring a regulatory overhaul. Yet the government and industry have opposed such proposals. Their stated reasons include “technical difficulties” and “high costs,” but they have also made the absurd argument that isolation is in “the interest of fishermen.” Citing a case in which a fisherman jumped into the sea after receiving distressing news from home, they claimed that contact with family could negatively affect fishermen’s mental health.

Government enforcement of laws protecting foreign fishermen is selective. For example, it is common for employers to hold workers’ passports—a recognized indicator of forced labor. Nonetheless, the government defends this practice by accepting employers’ explanations that they keep passports “to avoid delays in passport renewal on behalf of fishermen.” Furthermore, the government repeatedly insists that labor laws do not apply to fishing boats flying the Taiwanese flag, unreasonably claiming that such vessels are not an extension of national territory and are therefore beyond the reach of labor law enforcement. Yet in other contexts, the government invokes extraterritorial criminal law to assert sovereignty. In other words, jurisdiction and borders remain flexible—whenever it is convenient.

4. Foreign Factory Workers: Disparities between Law and Reality

Compared to foreign domestic caregivers and fishermen, foreign factory workers are better off because they are protected under the Labor Standards Act. Despite this, structural constraints and labor rights violations remain commonplace. One example of the gap between law and reality is that female workers are often—illegally—required to take birth control pills or have IUDs inserted as a precondition for employment, even though the government claims to support reproductive rights for women workers regardless of nationality. Formal legal protections do not remedy these practices, as control over female migrant workers’ bodies is rationalized through economic logic.

In the name of enhancing representativeness and diversity, the government may invite migrant worker representatives to participate in policy-making processes, such as serving on the Committee of the New Immigrants Development Fund (which distributes resources to facilitate the accommodation and

integration of immigrants). However, such measures risk becoming mere tokenism: migrants' voices do not necessarily influence outcomes, as the government retains final decision-making power and most discussions are held in confidence, excluding the broader migrant population.

5. Refugees: Constant Resistance to Institutionalized Asylum

Most refugees and asylum seekers in Taiwan come from Southeast Asia, often entering on short-term visas. Taiwan has yet to enact a Refugee Law or ratify the 1951 Refugee Convention. This legal vacuum renders asylum seekers both invisible and unprotected under the law.

Participants observed that the “lack of social consensus” is the main reason the government resists calls to pass a refugee law. However, public opinion polls show sympathy and support for asylum seekers and refugees. It is the government—not the general public—that remains conservative and passive regarding refugees' human rights.

For stateless or undocumented asylum seekers, the government tends to rely on ad hoc, short-term harboring rather than institutionalized, long-term asylum. Those accommodated in shelters often face restrictions on freedom of movement and are even prohibited from contacting NGOs—measures framed as “protection” but, in effect, functioning as strict control.

II. Challenges of HRJ

To begin with, the government's justifications for rejecting human rights advocacy—such as citing “insufficient societal consensus,” “national security,” or the adequacy of existing measures—are always challenging to counter. It is not necessarily the case that human rights justifications (HRJ) are more difficult to address than non-HRJ excuses in terms of persuading the government and effecting change. However, participants pointed out that HRJ is distinct in that it raises the technical and knowledge threshold required to effectively challenge the government's claims.

While it may seem encouraging that the government adopts the language of human rights to defend its policies—creating an impression of greater human rights sensitivity and opening space for international dialogue and human rights monitoring—this also heightens the expertise needed for NGOs to meaningfully engage. Legislators unfamiliar with these issues may also find it harder to hold the executive accountable, as HRJ can make government positions sound plausible and facially legitimate. Moreover, the government can strategically include symbolic representatives or make public participation excessively burdensome, entangling stakeholders in bureaucratic red tape and curtailing genuine reform. Such tactics consume the already limited resources and energy of NGOs, which often operate under funding and staffing constraints.

The adoption of UN human rights instruments and the establishment of review mechanisms have increased the use of HRJ in state reports and related government documents. However, such justifications often amount to lip service to review committees and civil society pressure, rather than genuine policy transformation. The government's rights discourse can also shift depending on its

audience—international or domestic. For example, during periodic reviews of UN human rights conventions, the government claims to provide “respite services” to families employing domestic caregivers so that caregivers can take paid leave without leaving employers unsupported. Yet, to a domestic audience, the government openly frames respite services as a benefit for nationals, explicitly disconnecting them from migrant workers’ working conditions.

Ultimately, many human rights issues require institutional change, but the government often lacks the political will to pursue meaningful reform. In such cases, it may resort to convenient HRJ or superficial measures that can be presented as advancing rights to a minimal degree, serving as substitutes for substantive action. For instance, there is no effective alternative for live-in foreign caregivers who become pregnant and cannot maintain a one-on-one care model. The government’s only solution is to provide shelter once the caregiver stops working, which fails to address the structural issue—the one-on-one live-in care model itself.

III. Possible Resistance

While participants emphasized the higher communication costs, shifting dynamics in policy dialogue, tokenism, and weakened accountability under HRJ, they did not view the phenomenon as wholly negative. HRJ can also create opportunities for NGOs. The universalist nature of human rights standards invites external scrutiny of Taiwan’s policies and offers NGOs a framework for engaging with international actors. For instance, human rights issues tend to resonate strongly with the EU, whereas the U.S. may prioritize specific rights concerns. When the government adopts HRJ terminology, domestic groups can leverage international pressure to push for policy change, rather than being confined to internal political channels.

For example, participants observed that the government often seeks to avoid meaningful reforms to its human rights obligations with repetitive excuses and bureaucratic obstructions. Recognizing that the Ministry of Labor and the Fisheries Agency are unlikely to implement major reforms concerning distant-water fishers, NGOs have instead turned to EU or U.S. rights watchdogs for leverage. In such cases, international human rights instruments provide a basis for negotiation, and drawing international attention can generate stronger external pressure on the government to move toward necessary reforms.

